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Key Points:

- A novel physics-informed machine learning method for developing continuous soil pedotransfer functions is introduced
- The method is suitable for data sets of SWRC with imbalanced and incomplete wet and dry measurements
- The SWRC derived from PINN is differentiable with respect to matric potential and can be integrated into numerical algorithms

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Physics-Informed Neural Networks for Estimating a Continuous Form of the Soil Water Retention Curve From Basic Soil Properties

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Abstract This paper presents a novel physics-informed neural network (PINN) approach for developing pedotransfer functions (PTFs) to predict continuous soil water retention curves (SWRCs) based on soil textural fractions, organic carbon content, and bulk density. In contrast to conventional parametric PTFs developed for specific SWRC models, the PINN learns a non-specific form of the SWRC from both measurements and physical constraints imposed during the training process. This approach allows the estimated SWRC to maintain its physical integrity from saturation to oven-dry conditions, even in scenarios with sparse data. The new approach is particularly effective for tackling the challenges encountered in developing PTFs on large SWRC data sets, which often have an imbalance toward the wet-end ($pF \leq 4.2$) and include numerous samples with limited and unevenly distributed measurements, many of which do not meet the requirements to fit traditional SWRC models. We compared the performance of the PINN with that of a conventional physics-agnostic neural network using a data set of 4,200 soil samples. While both networks performed similarly at the wet-end where data are abundant, with RMSE values of around $0.041 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$, the PINN excelled at the dry-end ($pF > 4.2$) where data are sparse and unevenly distributed, achieving a normalized RMSE of 0.172 ($\text{RMSE} = 0.0045 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$) compared to a normalized RMSE of 0.522 ($\text{RMSE} = 0.0136 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$) for the conventional neural network. The SWRC derived from the PINN is differentiable with respect to matric potential, making it well-suited for integration into models of water flow in the unsaturated zone.

1. Introduction

A variety of hydrological processes at the land surface, including infiltration, evaporation, runoff, drainage and mass and energy exchange processes between the soil and atmosphere at different spatial scales are regulated by soil hydraulic properties (i.e., water retention and hydraulic conductivity). Therefore, developing methods for fast and accurate quantification of soil hydraulic properties is of crucial importance (Montzka et al., 2017; Norouzi et al., 2023).

The soil water retention curve (SWRC) describes the volume of water per volume of soil as a function of matric potential under equilibrium conditions. The SWRC is an essential hydrological property related to the soil pore space and the specific surface area of the soil particles. Hence, it is strongly affected by soil structure, texture, and soil constituents such as organic matter and clay minerals (Tuller & Or, 2005a). Despite its importance, measuring a complete SWRC from saturation to near-dry conditions using standard laboratory methods is time-consuming and costly and requires several devices, each for a certain range of matric potentials. These challenges increase toward the dry end of the SWRC. As a result, measured data on SWRC are limited, and the available data sets are generally imbalanced in favor of the wet end.

To address these challenges, soil pedotransfer functions (PTFs) for SWRC have been developed. A PTF is a mathematical model that relates the SWRC to easily measurable soil physical properties such as textural fractions, organic carbon content (OC), and bulk density (BD) that affect the SWRC (Saxton & Rawls, 2006; Weber et al., 2024). Two main types of PTFs are commonly used: point PTFs, which provide water contents at specific matric potentials, and parametric PTFs, which estimate parameters of specific SWRC models, such as Brooks and Corey (1965) or van Genuchten (1980), and provide predictions across the entire curve. Parametric PTFs can be enhanced with physical constraints (Lehmann et al., 2020) or a customized loss function (Minasny &

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McBratney, 2002) to generate a more meaningful and accurate set of parameters. However, a major limitation of parametric PTFs is the need for a sufficient number of well-distributed measurements across the entire matric potential range to accurately fit the model to the SWRC and obtain a meaningful and reliable set of parameters. Another major challenge is that these models cannot be fitted properly when measurements are available only from the dry or wet ends of the SWRC. Consequently, a significant portion of large SWRC data sets with limited or unevenly distributed measurements remains unused in the development of parametric PTFs. This, in turn, decreases the generalization capabilities of the PTFs.

A third category includes continuous PTFs that produce non-specific forms of the SWRC. Koekkoek and Bootink (1999) were among the first to incorporate soil matric potential as a predictor in the input layer of a neural network and develop point PTFs. The outputs of the neural network in this case are volumetric water contents corresponding to the matric potentials given as input. Jain et al. (2004) showed that a continuous, non-specific representation of the SWRC can be achieved by using soil matric potential as the input for a three-layer feed-forward neural network. Their results showed that the neural network can estimate a non-specific form of the SWRC with equal or greater accuracy than analytical hydraulic functions. Building on these studies, Haghverdi et al. (2012) added soil textural and physical properties as additional inputs to the neural network structure suggested by Jain et al. (2004) and developed continuous PTFs that learn the shape of the SWRC from basic soil measurements. The unique structure of these PTFs allows the incorporation of data sets with varying and incomplete numbers of measured water retention points. However, since the neural networks at the core of continuous PTFs entirely depend on measurements to learn the SWRC shape, the performance of these PTFs is highly influenced by the quality, density, and distribution of the SWRC measurements within the training set. Additionally, in scenarios with limited measurements, these models are prone to producing physically inconsistent predictions. As a result, their application under such conditions is generally not recommended (Haghverdi et al., 2014).

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) represent an innovative tool that overcomes the shortcomings of conventional machine learning techniques by integrating existing knowledge into the system. One common way to achieving this integration is by adding additional terms to the network's loss function. These terms penalize deviations from known physical behaviors, thus significantly constraining the space of admissible solutions. Consequently, the PINN not only learns from data but also adheres to physical constraints, ensuring more reliable and consistent predictions even in scenarios with sparse data (Degen et al., 2023; Moseley, 2022; Raissi et al., 2019; Willard et al., 2022).

PINNs and physics-informed machine learning methods have shown promising performance in vadose zone studies using synthetic data. These methods have been applied to estimate soil hydraulic properties from soil moisture and/or matric potential measurements (Tartakovsky et al., 2020), model water flow and solute transport using geoelectrical data (Haruzi & Moreno, 2023), and derive governing equations for soil water flow (Ghorbani et al., 2021).

In this study, we introduce a novel PINN designed to develop PTFs for the soil water retention curve. This PINN estimates a continuous, non-specific form of the SWRC based on soil textural and physical properties. Owing to the physical constraints incorporated into the model, the estimated SWRC is able to maintain its physical integrity even beyond the range of the training data. This capability makes the new approach particularly effective for tackling the challenges encountered in developing PTFs on large SWRC data sets, which are often imbalanced and contain a significant number of samples with incomplete or limited measurements, which do not meet the requirements to fit traditional SWRC models. We evaluate the performance of this new method using a comprehensive data set from Denmark and compare the results with those obtained from conventional physics-agnostic neural networks.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental Data

In this study, we rely on a comprehensive collection of soil samples, well distributed across Denmark. The main part of our data set consists of 4,047 soil samples (1,202 profiles) from an updated and unpublished version of the original Danish Soil Profile Database (Østergaard and Mamsen, 1990). The original Danish Soil Profile Database

include soil profile data collected at 7×7 km grid intersections nationwide. Soil samples were taken from two to six horizons per profile, with depths reaching approximately 170 cm.

Soil water retention measurements from this database cover only the wet end of the retention curve, with pF values ranging between 0 and 4.2, where pF is defined as the logarithm of the absolute value of matric potential in centimeters of water (i.e., $pF = \log_{10}|h|$). The distinction between the wet and dry ends of the soil water retention curve is based on the dominant forces affecting water retention. Below $pF = 4.2$, capillary forces primarily control water retention, while above this threshold, adsorptive forces begin to play a distinct and dominating role (Norouzi et al., 2022; Tuller & Or, 2005a).

Measurements were carried out using both the hanging water column ($pF \leq 2.0$) and pressure plate methods ($pF > 2.0$) (Dane & Hopmans, 2002; Tehrani et al., 2023) on undisturbed soil samples with a height 34.2 mm and a diameter of 60.1 mm. Bulk density was assessed by weighing dried (24 hr at 105°C) undisturbed soil samples. For a detailed description of this data set, refer to Østergaard and Mamsen (1990). Particle size distribution was determined through sieve and hydrometer methods (Gee & Or, 2002). To be able to effectively combine our different sources of texture measurements without any interpolation of particle sizes, the detailed texture fractions were grouped into three textural fractions based on the International Soil Science Society classification system (Hillel, 1982): clay ($< 2 \mu\text{m}$), silt ($2\text{--}20 \mu\text{m}$), and sand ($20\text{--}2,000 \mu\text{m}$). Soil organic carbon content was measured by dry combustion in a LECO induction furnace (Nelson & Sommers, 1982).

We calculated porosity using the equation $\text{porosity} = 1 - \rho_b/\rho_s$, where ρ_b is the bulk density and ρ_s is the particle density. The soil's saturated water content was assumed to be equal to the soil porosity. It was assigned at a pF value of -1 , which was assumed to be a safe threshold where all pores in the soil are saturated. Before applying the equation, we used the pedotransfer function developed by Marakkala Manage (2019) for Danish soils to modify ρ_s based on the organic carbon (OC) content. In cases where the calculated saturated water content was lower than the last measured point on the retention curve, we avoided adding the saturation point.

In addition to the Danish Soil Profile Database, a total of 154 SWRCs (127 profiles) from Danish soil samples from other studies were used which included dry-end measurements (i.e., $pF > 4.2$) of the SWRC. These studies included soil samples from Silstrup (Naveed et al., 2016), Estrup (Karup et al., 2017), Aarup (Deepagoda et al., 2013; Jensen et al., 2015), Saebj (Deepagoda et al., 2013; Jensen et al., 2015) and from the Danish Soil Library (Resurreccion et al., 2011) which are also distributed across Denmark.

For this group of soils, the wet end of the SWRCs, OC and BD were measured using a similar procedure explained above for the Danish Soil Profile Database. The SWRC measurements up to $pF = 3$ were taken on undisturbed soil core samples (100 cm^3), while measurements above $pF = 3$ were taken on loose, initially air-dry soil. The dry end of the SWRC ($pF > 4.2$) was measured with either the chilled mirror dewpoint method with a WP4-T Dewpoint Potentiometer (Resurreccion et al., 2011) or a Vapor Sorption Analyzer (VSA) (METER Group Inc., Pullman, WA, USA; Arthur et al., 2014) or both. In our data set, the WP4-T provided measured potentials close to $pF = 4.2$ and the VSA was used for matric potentials from $pF = 5$ to $pF = 6.6$. The high-resolution measurements of the VSA instrument were interpolated and reduced to three representative pFs at 5.3, 6.0, and 6.4. A comprehensive explanation of the procedures employed with the WP4-T and VSA can be found in Resurreccion et al. (2011) and Arthur et al. (2014), respectively.

The dominant texture of the collected soils is sand, comprising 1,093 samples, followed by sandy loam and loamy sand with 1,002 and 932 samples, respectively (Figure 1). The average value of OC is $0.0085 \text{ kg kg}^{-1}$ with a standard deviation of $0.0097 \text{ kg kg}^{-1}$. The average BD is $1,530 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ with a standard deviation of 170 kg m^{-3} . A detailed description of texture distribution across Denmark can be found in Adhikari et al. (2014).

The data set exhibits an imbalance in the availability of measurements from the dry- and wet-ends of the retention curve (Figure 2a). Specifically, 4,200 soil samples have measurements at the wet-end (i.e., $pF \leq 4.2$), while only 154 samples include the dry-end measurements (i.e., $pF > 4.2$). As depicted in Figure 2c, the number of measured points per retention curve ranges from 1 to over 10, with most samples having four to five points on their SWRC.

2.2. Neural Network Architecture and Physical Constraints

The main idea behind PINNs is to integrate physical principles and known relationships into the model training, thereby enhancing generalization capabilities and allowing the model to be trained with less data. Known physical

Figure 1. Soil textural distribution of 4,200 soil samples classified according to the ISSS (International Society of Soil Science) soil texture triangle. (a) Represents samples with dry-end measurements ($pF > 4.2$), while (b) shows samples with wet-end measurements ($pF \leq 4.2$). Blue circles represent the training set, and red circles represent the test set in both cases. H (heavy), L (light), Sa (sand), Si (silt), Cl (clay), and Lo (loam) are used to denote different soil texture classes.

principles can be incorporated into a machine learning model in several ways as reviewed by Willard et al. (2022). In our approach, this integration is achieved through the physics-informed design of the neural network structure (hard constraints) and regularization of the loss function, where additional terms are added to penalize deviations from physical laws (soft constraints).

In the subsequent sections we explain the architecture of the PINN for developing the continuous PTF along with the customized loss function. We then introduce the physical constraints and principles and the methods used for implementing them in the training of the neural network.

2.2.1. Neural Network Architecture

The feedforward neural network for development of the PTF consists of an input layer, two hidden layers and an output layer (Figure 3). The inputs to the neural network are sand (%), silt (%), clay (%), OC (%), BD (g cm^{-3}), and pF . By taking pF as an input, the neural network output is water content at the corresponding input pF , that is, $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$. In a conventional approach, the neural network is trained using a loss function that solely relies on data:

$$J = \frac{1}{N} \sum_I^N [\hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)} - \theta_{pF}^{(i)}]^2 \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$ and θ_{pF} are the predicted and measured water contents at the corresponding pF in the input layer, respectively, and N is the number of input examples. Once trained on a large number of input θ - pF pairs, the neural network can predict a complete SWRC based on sand, silt, clay, OC, and BD by continuously varying the pF values across the specified range of interest.

However, when we rely only on data for model training, the performance and shape of the continuous SWRC obtained from neural network is highly sensitive to the density and distribution of the provided water retention points in the training process (Haghverdi et al., 2014).

To address this issue, we use concepts from physics-informed neural networks and impose four physical constraints on the relation between pF in the input layer and water content in the output layer, $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$. In the next sections a detailed description of the physical constraints and the methods for implementing them are provided.

Figure 2. (a) Frequency distribution of samples with wet-end ($pF \leq 4.2$) and dry-end ($pF > 4.2$) measurements, (b) distribution of water retention measurements, and (c) frequency distribution of samples based on the number of available measured points on the soil water retention curves.

This mathematically translates to:

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dpF^2} = 0, pF > pF_{\text{thres}} \quad (2)$$

2.2.2. Monotonicity Constraint

A SWRC, when plotted in $pF-\theta$ space, is inherently a decreasing function (Figure 4). This means as soil dries out (i.e., pF increases), soil water content decreases. In parametric PTFs, this monotonic behavior is ensured by the fixed model form. However, the neural network shown in Figure 3 learns the relationship between pF and $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$ without a predefined SWRC form. As a result, it lacks an intrinsic understanding of this decreasing relationship. This can lead to violations of monotonicity, especially in areas with sparse and incomplete data. To address this issue, we impose a monotonically decreasing constraint between pF and $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$.

Generally, there are two approaches to implementing monotonicity in neural networks. This can be done by constructing inherently monotonic architectures (Daniels & Velikova, 2010; Milani Fard et al., 2016) or enforcing monotonicity during training through devising a modified loss function or a regularization term (Gupta et al., 2019). The former involves designing neural networks that guarantee monotonicity by their structure, while the latter achieves monotonic behavior through modifications in the loss functions or regularization techniques. In this study, we employ the method which falls under the first category, introduced by Runje and Shankaranarayana (2023) to apply the monotonicity constraint, which offers ease of implementation and computational efficiency.

Shortly, this method involves constructing two additional activation functions from a typical unsaturated monotonic activation function, such as Exponential Linear Unit (ELU). One of these functions is bounded, while the other is a concave, upper-bounded function. Each function is applied to different subsets of neurons in a layer. By combining the three activation functions, including the original ELU, the bounded function, and the concave upper-bounded function, the model effectively represents non-convex, monotonic continuous functions.

While a monotonically decreasing relationship between the model output $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$ and pF in the input layer is imposed, the relationship between the model output and other inputs remains non-monotonic and unconstrained.

2.2.3. Linear Behavior at the Dry End of the SWRC

Water is held in soil in two forms: (a) capillary water occupying the spaces between soil particles, and (b) adsorbed water forming a thin film around soil particles (Tuller et al., 1999). Typically, in soils that are not fully saturated, both forms of water, capillary and adsorbed, are present simultaneously (refer to Figure 7 in Tuller and Or (2005b)). As the soil begins to dry, capillary water recedes into the corners of the pores, and beyond a specific threshold matric potential, the water predominantly remains as adsorbed water films.

Experimental evidence shows that in the adsorbed water dominant region at the dry end, the soil water retention curve exhibits a linear behavior in a $pF-\theta$ space (Campbell & Shiozawa, 1992). In our analysis of 154 samples containing dry-end measurements, we found an average R-squared value of 0.985 when fitting a linear model to the dry-end data.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of the physics-informed neural network (PINN) with customized loss function used for the development of the continuous pedotransfer function (PTF). Automatic differentiation is used to compute partial derivative of $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$ with respect to pF , which are required for imposing the physical constraints. OC, organic carbon content; BD, bulk density; $pF = \log|\psi|$, where ψ is the soil matric potential in cm of water. Lambdas (λ) are weights for each term in the loss function and $S_1, S_2, S_3,$ and S_4 are the number of residual points in sets 1, 2, 3, and 4 for imposing the constraints. The monotonic behavior of pF and $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$ is enforced through the use of monotonic activation functions. Note that the number of units (nodes) in the hidden layers is reduced here for illustration and does not reflect the actual model (refer to Table 1 for actual values).

where pF_{thres} denotes a texture-dependent threshold pF value, beyond which linear behavior is observed (refer to Figure 3 of Norouzi et al. (2022)). However, regardless of soil texture, $pF_{thres} = 5$ is considered a universal threshold, above which the soil water is always in adsorbed form across various soil types (Tuller & Or, 2005a), leading to linear behavior at the dry end of the SWRCs (Figure 4).

We enforced linear behavior at the dry end of the SWRC within our neural network by adding an additional term to the loss function that penalizes the solution at a set of residual (collocation) points, when the linearity is

Figure 4. Examples of soil water retention curves with dry- and wet-end measurements for three soils with different textures, demonstrating the monotonic behavior between pF and water content, and linear behavior at pF s above 5. The full range of the retention curve is shown on the right, and a zoomed-in version of the dry end is shown on the left.

Figure 5. (a) Set 1 of the residual points in the space of inputs for enforcing linear behavior at the dry end, (b) set 2 (green scatters) and set 3 (blue scatters) of the residual points for bounding the range of pF at zero water content, (c) set 4 of the residual points for enforcing zero derivative below $pF = -0.3$. Note that the input space includes additional features including silt, OC, and BD, but for illustrative purposes, only clay, sand, and pF are plotted here.

violated. These residual points are arbitrary points within the input space whose pF s are greater than 5. Specifically, we generate N samples with arbitrary sand, silt, clay, OC, and BD combinations, to which we then assign random pF values between 5 and 7.6 as their last feature to create our set 1 of residual points. These randomly generated residual points are visualized in Figure 5a.

During each training step of the neural network, the second derivative of the output, $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$, with respect to pF is evaluated at these residual points by using automatic differentiation (Baydin et al., 2018). To guide the model toward linear behavior at the dry end, we add the mean absolute sum of these second derivatives to the custom loss function (third term of the loss function in Figure 3 and Equation 4). This additional term serves as a penalty for any non-linear solutions, where the second derivative deviates from zero, thereby enforcing linearity at the dry end of the SWRC.

2.2.4. Implementation of the Physical Range of pF at Hypothetical Zero Water Content

The range of soil matric potential at zero water content (pF_0) has been investigated in a number of studies (Arthur et al., 2013; Karup et al., 2017; Lu & Khorshidi, 2015; Schneider & Goss, 2012). This is typically done by linearly extrapolating the dry-end of the SWRC to zero water content since measuring matric potential at this water content is unfeasible (Figure 4). Karup et al. (2017) analyzed 171 undisturbed soil samples of varied textures and organic carbon contents. Their results showed that pF_0 varies between 6.65 and 7.1. Similarly, Arthur et al. (2013) identified pF_0 to vary between 6.5 and 7.45. Based on these findings, we set a constraint in our neural network model to maintain pF_0 within the range of 6.2–7.6. This broader range, compared to Karup et al. (2017) and Arthur et al. (2013), accommodates potential soils not covered in their studies.

The specified range of pF_0 is implemented in our neural network by incorporating penalizing terms into the loss function. When pF_0 falls within the specified range, two conditions are simultaneously met (Figure 6a). The predicted water content at $pF = 6.2$ is positive (condition 1) and the predicted soil-water content at $pF = 7.6$ is negative (condition 2). Figures 6b and 6c depict instances where this constraint is violated and pF_0 falls outside the specified range. In these two cases, either condition 1 or condition 2 is not met.

Building upon these two conditions that must be satisfied, we generate two separate combinations of M samples with arbitrary sand, silt, clay, OC, and BD values. We then add $pF = 6.2$ and $pF = 7.6$ as the last feature to each of these combinations to create set 2 and set 3 of residual points within the input space, respectively. The residual points in sets 2 and 3 are visualized in Figure 5b. According to Figure 6a, in order to meet conditions 1 and 2, the neural network predictions for set 2 of the residual points must be positive and the neural network predictions for set 3 of the residual points must be negative. During each training iteration, we predict the water content for sets 2 and 3 and add penalty terms (fourth and fifth terms in the loss function in Figure 3) to the custom loss function to penalize deviations from conditions 1 and 2, thereby enforcing the specified range of pF_0 .

Figure 6. Sketch illustrating the signs of the values of water content at $pF = 6.2$ and $pF = 7.6$ when (a) pF at zero water content (pF_0) falls within the specified range, and (b, c) when pF_0 falls outside the specified range.

2.2.5. Constant Water Content Constraint Below Air-Entry Pressure

The soil air-entry value, or bubbling pressure, is defined as the matric potential at which air invades the largest pore (Fredlund & Xing, 1994; Sourmanabad et al., 2024). According to this definition, when the soil matric potential, expressed in terms of pF , is below a specific value, the soil remains fully saturated and invariant to changes in matric potential. This can be mathematically expressed as:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dpF} = 0, \quad pF < pF_{\text{air-entry}} \quad (3)$$

The air-entry value, $pF_{\text{air-entry}}$, is influenced by both soil texture and structure, and is typically lower for coarse-textured soils (Rawls et al., 1982). To incorporate this constraint into our neural network, we set $pF = -0.3$ (equivalent to a matric potential of -0.5 cm) as the lowest threshold, below which the soil water content remains unchanged regardless of changes in soil matric potential. As illustrated in Figure 5c, we generate the set 4 of residual points that are randomly distributed within the input space with pF values ranging between -0.3 and -2.0 (equivalent to a matric potential of -0.01 cm). During each training step, we evaluate Equation 3 at these points and penalize deviations from this physical constraint by adding the sixth term to the loss function in Figure 3.

2.2.6. Loss Function

The neural network represented in Figure 3 is trained based on the measurements and physical constraints imposed using the following customized loss function:

$$J = \frac{\lambda_1}{N_{\text{wet}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{wet}}} [\hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)} - \theta_{pF}^{(i)}]^2 + \frac{\lambda_2}{N_{\text{dry}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{dry}}} [\hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)} - \theta_{pF}^{(i)}]^2 + \frac{\lambda_3}{S_1} \sum_{i=1}^{S_1} \left| \frac{\partial^2 \hat{\theta}_{pF}}{\partial pF^2} \right|^{(i)} + \frac{\lambda_4}{S_2} \sum_{i=1}^{S_2} |\min(0, \hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)})| + \frac{\lambda_5}{S_3} \sum_{i=1}^{S_3} |\max(0, \hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)})| + \frac{\lambda_6}{S_4} \sum_{i=1}^{S_4} \left| \frac{\partial \hat{\theta}_{pF}}{\partial pF} \right|^{(i)} \quad (4)$$

where lambdas (λ) are weights for each term in the loss function. These weights control the relative contribution of each component of the loss function during the training process. The optimized values of these weights are obtained in the hyperparameter optimization step, as explained in the next section. The first two terms in Equation 4 represent the mean squared error (MSE) between the volumetric water contents predicted by the neural network and the actual measurements, where N_{wet} and N_{dry} are the number of training examples from the wet- and

dry-ends, respectively. We employ separate terms for the wet-end (i.e., $pF \leq 4.2$) and dry-end (i.e., $pF > 4.2$) inputs to account for the disparities in sample sizes between the dry- and wet-ends, as well as the significantly narrower range of water contents observed at the dry-end. These two terms, referred to as “data loss” in Figure 3, represent the supervised error between the measured and predicted values (Willard et al., 2022).

The last four terms in Equation 4, referred to as “physics loss” in Figure 3, are added to ensure consistency with physical laws. In particular, the third term in Equation 4 enforces linearity at the dry-end by setting the second derivatives for set 1 of the residual points (Figure 5a) to zero. The fourth and fifth terms ensure that pF_0 remains within the specified range by requiring that the model predictions at sets 2 and 3 of residual points (Figure 5b) are positive and negative, respectively. The last term in Equation 4 forces the water content to remain constant for values of pF lower than -0.3 by setting the first derivative for set 4 of the residual points (Figure 5c) to zero. S_1 , S_2 , S_3 , and S_4 are the number of residual points in sets 1, 2, 3, and 4.

To accommodate the customized loss function in Equation 4, which incorporates separate terms for the dry- and wet-ends, we allocated 70% of the measurements from each of the wet- and dry-ends for training and validation, and the remaining 30% for testing as a hold-out set to assess the model performance. This data partitioning strategy ensures that the specified percentages of each part of the data are included in the final training, validation, and testing sets, and that the final split sets are representative of the entire data set. In total, we had 1,329 soil profiles, of which 930 profiles (15,692 $pF - \theta$ pairs) were used for training and validation, and 399 profiles (6,864 $pF - \theta$ pairs) were reserved for the test set.

Given the high correlation between water content measurements within a single soil sample, and to prevent data leakage between the training and testing sets, we split the data by soil samples rather than individual pairs of $pF - \theta$ measurements. This approach ensures that all measurements (i.e., $pF - \theta$ pairs) from a particular soil sample are exclusively in either the training or testing set. We applied the same strategy to soil profiles, guaranteeing that data from all horizons within a profile are contained entirely within either the training or testing set.

2.2.7. Hyperparameter Optimization

The performance of a neural network is strongly impacted by the hyperparameters that determine its architecture and learning process. To identify the optimum hyperparameter set, we applied the Bayesian optimization (Snoek et al., 2012) to the training and validation sets. Bayesian optimization is a method that surpasses traditional grid or random search techniques in efficiency by using a probabilistic model to direct the search toward favorable regions of the parameter space, thereby reducing the number of iterations required to find superior hyperparameters. The analysis was conducted using the TensorFlow package in Python (Abadi et al., 2016).

We determined the optimal number of hidden layers, units per layer, initial learning rate, decay rate, and decay step through Bayesian optimization. Other hyperparameters, such as the number of residual points in various sets and the penalizing factors, were manually fine-tuned. Our analysis indicated that approximately 1,500 residual points within the input space suffice to maintain linearity at the dry-end (Figure 5a), whereas 500 residual points were adequate for enforcing the pF_0 specified range (Figure 5b). For enforcing the invariant behavior of water content with respect to pF for pFs lower than -0.3 , we used 1,500 residual points (Figure 5c). The weights for each term in the loss function are reported in Table 1. Notably, the fine-tuned weight for the dry-end loss term in Equation 4, λ_2 , was 10, which closely matches the ratio of average water contents between the wet and dry ends, calculated as 9.49.

We utilized the Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) activation function across the network (Clevert et al., 2015). Compared to the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), which outputs zero for negative inputs and can lead to inactive neurons, ELU produces negative outputs for negative inputs. This helps prevent neurons from becoming inactive, which is a common issue with ReLU. Additionally, by generating smooth and non-zero gradients even for negative inputs, ELU maintains a more balanced gradient flow, reducing the likelihood of vanishing gradient problems and facilitating faster and more stable learning. Furthermore, to prevent overfitting, a dropout layer with a 40% rate was applied before the output layer. This layer serves as a regularization by randomly dropping units (along with their connections) during training, preventing the neural network from heavily relying on specific units. Additionally, L2 regularization (Ridge Regularization) with a strength of 0.02 was applied to the second hidden layer, which helps prevent overfitting by penalizing large weights in the network (Ng, 2004).

Table 1
The Optimized Hyperparameters of the Neural Network

Hyperparameter	Value
Number of hidden layers	2
Number of neurons per hidden layer	54 (hidden layer 1), 251 (hidden layer 2)
Initial learning rate, decay rate, decay step	0.0195, 0.96, 312
Batch size	32
Number of epochs ^a	50
Activation function	Elu
Optimizer	Adam
$\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5, \lambda_6$ ^b	1.0, 10.0, 1.0, 1,000.0, 1,000.0, 1.0
S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4 ^c	1,500, 500, 500, 1,500

^aAn epoch refers to one complete iteration over the entire training data set, after which the model parameters are updated.
^bLambda (λ) refers to the weight assigned to each term in the loss function (Figure 3). ^cS represents the number of points in different sets of residuals used to apply physical constraints in the model (Figure 3).

2.2.8. Evaluation Criteria

The model performance was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE), the coefficient of determination (R-squared), and mean bias error (MBE) of predicted and measured volumetric water contents:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)} - \theta_{pF}^{(i)})^2} \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)} - \theta_{pF}^{(i)})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (\theta_{pF}^{(i)} - \bar{\theta}_{pF})^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{MBE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{\theta}_{pF}^{(i)} - \theta_{pF}^{(i)}) \quad (7)$$

where N is the number of observations, θ_{pF} is the measured water content, $\bar{\theta}_{pF}$ is the average value of the measured water contents, and $\hat{\theta}_{pF}$ is the predicted water content by neural network. To make a comparable analysis of the model performance at the dry- and wet-ends of the test data set, which have significantly different ranges of values, we additionally calculated the normalized root mean squared error (nRMSE), given as:

$$\text{nRMSE} = \frac{\text{RMSE}}{\bar{\theta}_{pF}} \quad (8)$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Physics Informed Neural Network Performance

The SWRC obtained from the PINN for various soil samples with varying textures and percentages of OC are presented in Figure 7. It should be noted that, in contrast to parametric PTFs, where a specific form of the SWRC is fitted individually for each sample, the PINN learns the underlying relationship between soil properties (sand, silt, clay, organic carbon, and bulk density) and the SWRC, along with the shape of the SWRC, during the training process. This is achieved by minimizing the objective function (Equation 4) for all samples simultaneously. Through this process, the model captures the general pattern of SWRCs from the training set as well as the physical constraints guiding its learning. By leveraging the data set as a whole, the model can predict SWRCs even for soils with only a few measured points. This approach is particularly useful for more complex soils, such

Figure 7. The predicted SWRCs (blue line) using the physics-informed neural network for various soils with varying clay and organic carbon contents and different numbers of measurement points on the retention curve (red dots).

as those with bimodal distributions, although the Danish soils in this study predominantly exhibit unimodal behavior.

The non-specific form of the SWRCs discovered from measurements and physical constraints show a pattern consistent with the wet region of the sigmoidal models for the SWRC (Kosugi, 1994; van Genuchten, 1980), and then transition to a linear behavior in the dry region, in line with physical constraints applied during model training. Specifically, all curves demonstrate monotonically decreasing trends, with linear behavior observed at pF s greater than 5.0, and the pF at zero water content falls within the 6.2 to 7.6 range. In addition, for all curves, if pF values are lower than -0.3 , the water content remains invariant with respect to soil pF .

Figure 8. The detailed performance of the PINN across the wet ($pF \leq 4.2$) and dry ($pF > 4.2$) end water retention data of the test set. The overall RMSE, nRMSE, and R-squared were $0.041 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$, 0.17, and 0.92, respectively. The dashed line depicts the line of equality.

The extent of linear behavior at the dry end of the SWRC varies significantly with the soil specific surface area, which is largely influenced by its clay content (Norouzi et al., 2022; Tuller & Or, 2005a). To enforce the linear behavior at the dry-end, where soil water is mainly in adsorbed form, we set $pF = 5$ as a threshold above which even high-clay-content soils exhibit linear behavior. This linear region extends to pFs lower than this threshold in soils with lower clay and OC content, such as samples 1, 2, and 3 (Figure 7). This is because sandy soils have a narrower pore size distribution due to their narrow particle size distribution (Norouzi et al., 2021). Consequently, upon drying, a slight increase in soil suction causes capillary water to recede rapidly, resulting in a dominance of adsorbed water with a linear dry-end behavior.

Our data set (Figure 2c) includes a significant number of soil samples with fewer than five measurements (e.g., samples 1, 2, 9, and 11 in Figure 7) and some with measurements only at the dry-end (e.g., sample 4). In contrast to parametric PTFs, which require a certain number of well-distributed measurements for fitting a specific model (Børgesen & Schaap, 2005; Schaap & Leij, 1998), continuous non-specific PTFs can integrate incomplete and unevenly distributed measurements into the training process. This flexibility offers a distinct advantage over parametric PTFs, which are restricted by the necessity for complete and uniformly distributed measurements. This limitation prevents parametric PTFs from utilizing all available SWRC measurements within a data set.

The trained PINN obtained an overall RMSE of 0.040 and $0.041 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ on the train and test sets, respectively. In Figure 8, the performance of the PINN at the wet and dry-ends of the test set is presented in terms of normalized RMSE and R-squared (R^2). The PINN achieved an RMSE of $0.0045 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ and a nRMSE of 0.172 at the dry end of the test set. Despite the significant imbalance in the data set (Figure 2a), the performance at the dry end, where there are far fewer samples in the training set, remains very close to both the overall performance and the performance at the wet-end. The model performance on the wet part of the data set containing the dry-end measurements was $0.037 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$. The small MBE values, $0.0006 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ for the dry end and $-0.0025 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ for the wet end, indicate that the PINN did not exhibit any systematic bias.

The PINN performance at the dry-end is comparable to that of several PTFs specifically developed for the dry end of the SWRC (Arthur et al., 2013; Pittaki-Chrysodonta et al., 2019), and even outperforms some others (Jensen et al., 2015). These comparable results confirm that the PINN developed in this study effectively captures the maximum correlation between soil texture, bulk density (BD), organic carbon (OC), and water contents at the dry-end when data from both the dry- and wet-ends are combined.

Børgesen and Schaap (2005) and Børgesen et al. (2008) developed parametric PTFs using neural networks for estimating the van Genuchten (1980) retention parameters and tested their models using part of the wet-end data set used in this study. They reported an RMSE of $0.049 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ for a model that incorporated sand, silt, clay, bulk density and organic matter as inputs, which is lower than the performance of the PINN on the wet-end with an RMSE of $0.042 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ on a larger data set (Figure 8). Additionally, they reported RMSE values of $0.055 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ for the Rosetta model (Schaap et al., 2001) and $0.044 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ for the Wösten et al. (1999) model when applied to

Figure 9. (a) The normalized RMSE and (b) R-squared of the PINN in comparison with the conventional neural network at the dry- and wet-end water retention data of the test set with 212 and 6,652 measured $pF - \theta$ pairs, respectively.

the wet end of the data set used in this study, both of which demonstrate lower performance compared to the PINN. It is worth noting that Børgesen and Schaap (2005) were able to use only 50% of the data set for training, which included samples with at least five retention points (-1 , -3 , -10 , -100 , and $-1,500$ kPa). In contrast, the PINN does not rely on a minimum number of data points for fitting, making it more versatile for handling sparse or incomplete data sets.

The lowest performance across the soil classes was observed for the Loam class with an RMSE of $0.073 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$, followed by the Heavy Clay class with an RMSE of $0.065 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$. These two classes made up less than 1% of the entire data set. Beyond these two soil classes, the model's performance improved significantly, with RMSE values scattered around the average.

3.2. Performance of Physics-Informed and Conventional (Physics-Agnostic) Neural Networks

The performance of the PINN and the conventional physics-agnostic neural network, which uses the loss function defined in Equation 1 are compared in Figure 9. As seen, at the wet-end, both networks exhibit nearly similar performance. The close performance at this end is expected because with abundant data at the wet-end in the training set with approximately 17,500 measured points (i.e., training examples), the conventional neural network is able to learn the underlying relationships between the model inputs and outputs merely from data (Tartakovsky et al., 2020).

The dependency of the performance of the physics-agnostic continuous PTFs on the amount and resolution of the measurements was investigated in the study of Haghverdi et al. (2018). They observed an improvement in the model performance when they used the high-resolution measurements acquired by the HYPROP system (Peters & Durner, 2008) that typically produces about 10 times more water retention data compared to the traditional equilibrium approach that provides fragmentary measurements across a few pFs .

In contrast to the wet-end, at the dry-end, the PINN with a nRMSE of 0.172 significantly outperformed the conventional NN, which obtained a nRMSE of 0.522. This performance highlights the benefits of PINNs when dealing with limited and sparse data sets at the dry-end. The success of the PINN can be partially attributed to the constraints imposed on the solution space. Specifically, solutions at the dry-end that violate either the linear behavior or the predefined pF range at zero water content are penalized. This mechanism effectively narrows the range of possible solutions, thereby reducing the amount of data required to discern underlying relationships.

Another key factor in the higher performance of the PINN at the dry-end lies in the fact that we consider a separate loss term for dry-end measurements with a high weight [second term in Equation 4]. Dry-end measurements are on average an order of magnitude lower than the wet-end measurements. This results in significantly smaller error residuals for dry-end data in the loss function. Consequently, when a single-term loss function is applied uniformly across both the wet and dry-ends, the limited data points from the dry-end with their small residuals have a negligible contribution to the overall loss. This prevents the model from accurately converging to the dry-end measurements. As a result, a customized approach that knowingly accounts for the variance in measurement scales between dry- and wet-ends is required.

Figure 10. The model performance at the dry-end for various number of dry-end measurements in the training set.

Data for the dry end of the SWRC is relatively rare compared to the wet end. This is due to previous challenges in measurement methodology. To determine the tolerance of the PINN to lack of dry-end measurements, we progressively reduced the number of dry-end measurements in the training set while evaluating the model performance on the original test set for the dry-end. As shown in Figure 10, the PINN maintained its performance on the dry end with up to 100 dry-end retention points. Beyond this threshold, the performance began to degrade. This high tolerance to sparse measurements at the dry end is primarily attributed to the strong guidance from physical constraints within the PINN.

To illustrate the capabilities of the PINN, predictions from both the PINN and a conventional physics-agnostic neural network are plotted for a sample from the test set in Figure 11. Both models were trained using only wet-end measurements ($pF \leq 4.2$) but were extrapolated to the dry-end region. As depicted, the conventional network fails to extrapolate to pF s above 4.2 and produces unrealistic predictions close to saturation, where monotonicity is violated. This non-monotonic behavior is more likely to occur in samples that are less frequent in the data set, such as the one with 17% clay content in

Figure 11, which is typical for Danish soils. In contrast, the PINN maintains its monotonic behavior throughout the entire range, exhibits linear behavior at the dry end despite the absence of training data from this region. Additionally, pF_0 of PINN remains within the specified range. This guidance effectively narrows the solution space, allowing the PINN to be trained with fewer measurements and extrapolate beyond the range of training data.

4. Conclusions and Outlook

In this study, we employed a physics-informed neural network (PINN) method to develop a continuous pedo-transfer function for the soil water retention curve (SWRC) that learns the shape of the soil water retention curve through both data and physical principles. Specifically, we imposed four constraints on the relationship between pF in the input layer and water content in the output layer: a monotonically decreasing constraint between pF and water content (θ), enforcing linear behavior for pF above 5 (adsorbed water dominant region), setting a specified range for pF at zero water content (pF_0), and enforcing constant water content constraint below air-entry pressure.

The model was trained on a large data set of SWRC measurements with a significant imbalance in the number of measurements, favoring the wet-end ($pF < 4.2$) over the dry-end ($pF > 4.2$).

At the wet end, where measurements are abundant, the PINN and the conventional physics-agnostic neural network performed similarly. However, at the dry end, where measurements are scarce due to previous challenges involved in data collection, the physics-informed model significantly outperformed the conventional network. The proposed model is particularly well-suited for dealing with the challenges associated by imbalanced, incomplete, and unevenly distributed data sets of SWRCs.

The results indicated that even in regions with sufficient data, the non-specific form of the SWRC developed with a conventional unconstrained neural network is still prone to producing physically unrealistic predictions. Consequently, the use of such neural networks is not recommended. In contrast, owing to the inherent differentiability of neural networks, the SWRC derived from the PINN is differentiable with respect to pF and can be integrated into the numerical schemes and algorithms developed for solving the governing equations of water flow in the unsaturated zone (i.e., Richards' equation).

In this study, the monotonicity constraint was enforced by modifying the neural network activation functions, ensuring that it is always satisfied. In contrast, the remaining constraints were incorporated by introducing penalty

Figure 11. Predicted soil water retention curves (SWRCs) using physics-informed (PINN) and conventional neural networks for a soil sample with sand, silt, clay, and organic carbon equal to 74%, 9%, 17%, and 0.1%, respectively. Both models are trained only using the wet-end measurements ($pF \leq 4.2$).

terms into the loss function. While the activation-based approach guarantees strict adherence to the constraint, the effectiveness of the penalty-based method is influenced by the number of residual points and the assigned weights within the loss function. For example, as shown in Figure 7, the constraint enforcing constant water content below the air-entry pressure is better satisfied in sandy soils compared to finer-textured soils. Future research should focus on optimizing the number of residual points and the penalty weights to enhance the enforcement of physical constraints without compromising the overall model performance.

Incorporating additional environmental covariates offers potential for improving the model's predictions, especially in digital soil mapping (Gupta et al., 2021; Hengl et al., 2017). Variables such as climate, topography, and land use could enhance the PINN's ability to predict soil hydraulic properties and map soil water retention characteristics more accurately.

In contrast to conventional parametric PTFs, which are developed for specific forms of SWRC models and require a certain number of well-distributed measurements for fitting the model of interest, the structure of the PINN allows for integrating all available measurements in the model training, regardless of the number of measured points on the SWRC. This capability is crucial for our ongoing research into digital mapping of soil hydraulic properties, as maximizing the use of all available measurements can enhance spatial coverage and improve predictions (Norouzi, Tuller, et al., 2024).

Data Availability Statement

The data set used as input in this study is accessible via Norouzi, Pesch, et al. (2024).

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